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[Zamani Mahmoud](#), Zamani Iman, Shafiee Masoud, Izadbakhsh Alireza (2024)

On the α -exponential stability of linear positive singular systems with multiple time-varying delays

Abstract: This paper deals with α -exponential stability analysis of the continuous-time linear positive singular systems with multiple time-varying delays. First, α -exponential stability problem of the single delay case is addressed. For this purpose, delay-range dependent sufficient conditions for such systems, which are regular and impulse-free, are stated in the paper. Then, α -exponential stability conditions for systems with multiple constant delays are addressed, and after that, we extend our idea for stability to multiple delays. To show the usefulness of the proposed conditions, two numerical and practical examples are given.

Keywords: Exponential stability, Multiple delays, Positive systems, Singular systems, Time-varying delay

[Mahmoud Zamani](#) Contact Info:

Phone: +1(585)6060944
email: mahmoud.zamani@rutgers.edu

[Mahmoud Zamani](#) Available at:

Google scholar: <https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=1axuoOAAAAAJ&hl=en&oi=ao>

Scopus: <https://www.scopus.com/authid/detail.uri?authorId=57302763500>

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4088-3798>

ResearchGate: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Mahmoud-Zamani?ev=hdr_xprf

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